

Thermal effusivity of different tabletop materials in relation to users' perception

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

School desk
Office desk
Ergonomics
Thermal comfort

ABSTRACT

Tactile interaction between humans and elements in the built environment, such as furniture, is often under-appreciated. The aim of this study was to objectively evaluate thermal properties of ten tabletop materials as well as user perceptions of those materials after use. Sixteen participants tested ten materials in a randomised order. Infrared thermography was used to determine tabletop temperature distribution and change. Materials with lower thermal effusivity (wood-based materials) in general reached higher surface temperature differences after 15 min of contact and were rated as more pleasant to touch, more suitable for writing, and more liked for everyday use. Participants' sex and forearm mass had no effect on the temperature after contact. Participants gave the highest ratings to the appearance of oak-based materials. Surface treatment affected subjective evaluation of the materials. The tabletop made of lacquered solid wood had the most favourable thermal and user-rated characteristics.

1. Introduction

Contact with different materials can affect personal comfort and, consequently, influence physical and mental well-being (Ikei et al., 2017a). However, in design, visual aesthetics are often prioritised over tactile interaction between the human and elements in the environment (Kotradyová, 2015). Tables (and desks) are key pieces of furniture that many people use daily at work, school or at home. Students and office workers spend up to 6 h of their school/working time seated at a table (Ee et al., 2018; Parry and Straker, 2013). Ergonomic design considers different aspects, such as user anthropometry, yet ergonomic suitability is not only dependent upon the dimensions of a product. Aspects such as sensory properties and contact comfort remain important but are often disregarded. Specifically, tabletop design often neglects ergonomic criteria and focuses mostly on appearance and manufacturer restrictions. However, people perceive a product as a whole, and their preference may depend on tactile sensations, such as hardness, roughness, and surface temperature, in addition to appearance (Schifferstein and Hekkert, 2007).

Critical aspect of thermal comfort is the surface temperature of the object a person interacts with (Wu et al., 1996) where heat transfer is considered to be an important factor influencing tactile sensations (Sakuragawa et al., 2008). Although thermal comfort is a subjective evaluation (ANSI/ASHRAE, 2017), methods to objectively assess temperature of the material have been used, including thermal sensors (Cengiz et al., 2007; Cengiz and Babalik, 2009) and infrared thermography (Koskelo et al., 2005; Sales et al., 2017). Thermal suitability of different materials for chair seats has been evaluated previously, whereas research assessing thermal suitability of different materials for tabletops is lacking.

Cengiz et al. (2007) reported minimal differences in thermal comfort between three different car seat materials (velvet, jacquard, microfibre). A subsequent study observed that in terms of thermal comfort participants preferred natural fibre ramie blended more than polyester seat covers (Cengiz and Babalik, 2009). Textile coverings have been found to improve physiological indicators of airplane seat comfort, with a fabric cover being a better choice than leather regarding sweat transport (Bartels, 2003). Kotradyová and Teischinger (2014a,b) evaluated

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apergo.2021.103664>

Received 8 March 2021; Received in revised form 25 November 2021; Accepted 2 December 2021

Available online 7 December 2021

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contact comfort of twelve different materials for chair seats, arm rests, and backrests. However, elements were not examined separately but as a whole. Participants rated contact comfort on scales assessing warmth, aesthetics, and overall comfort of materials. In this study, natural wood materials were rated as warmer than non-wooden materials (e.g., aluminium). In their study, greater thermal comfort was determined with a higher degree of perceived warmth of the material. Vlaović et al. (2012) also assessed the thermal suitability of different chairs and found a high positive correlation between subjectively evaluated and objectively measured temperatures in the seat region under the thigh, while no correlation was found for other body parts. Chair seats made of plywood maintained the lowest surface temperature, whereas solid wood, polyester fabric, and synthetic leather seat pans obtained the highest surface temperatures after 15 min (Sales et al., 2017).

When seated at the table, carrying out paperwork or working with a computer, the forearms are in constant touch with the tabletop. Studies have shown that contact with different materials can evoke different physiological responses and influence well-being (Ikei et al., 2017). Contact with acrylic plastic, kept at room temperature, can create uncomfortable sensations, with an associated significant increase in blood pressure (Sakuragawa et al., 2008), indicating a close correlation between subjective evaluation and physiological responses. Similarly, Ikei et al. (2017) showed that touching marble, tile, and stainless steel increased autonomic nervous activity, while no such effect was found for contact with wood.

No study that we are aware of has objectively evaluated surface temperature changes and perceptions of different materials used for office or school tabletops. This study aimed to investigate three main outcomes: i) physical measurements of the materials (thermal effusivity and emissivity), ii) surface temperature change of tabletops before and after 15 min of constant contact using infrared thermography, and iii) subjective evaluation of perception of different tabletop materials. The hypotheses were:

1. Natural wood materials will have higher surface temperature differences after 15 min of contact than non-wood materials.
2. The participants will rate natural wood materials as more visually pleasant than non-wood materials.
3. The participants will rate wood materials treated by lacquer as more suitable for handwriting and everyday use than untreated and oiled wood materials.
4. The participants will rate materials with higher surface temperature differences after 15 min of contact as the most suitable for everyday use.

2. Materials and methods

In order to evaluate the material temperature change after use and

Table 1
Model power based on Monte Carlo simulations.

Comparison	Indicator	% simulations passing	95% CI of expected simulations to pass
Temperature difference between materials (pre-stage)	Mean temperature	48.00%	44.86%–51.15%
Temperature difference between materials at pre- and post-stage	Mean temperature	100%	99.63%–100%
Temperature difference between materials at pre- and post-stage	10th percentile of temperature	100%	99.63%–100%
Temperature difference between materials at pre- and post-stage	90th percentile of temperature	100%	99.63%–100%

user perception of tabletops, we developed a table frame with exchangeable tops. Ten tabletops (Table 2) were made of different materials with different types of finishing commonly used in the production of tabletops. The study was approved by the National Medical Ethics Committee (0120-631/2017/2) and registered at Clinical Trials (NCT03733366).

2.1. Participants

A sample of 16 healthy participants (10 females and 6 males, mean age = 25.9, SD = 4.0) participated in the study, which is in concordance with previous research investigating thermal comfort of different materials (Cengiz et al., 2007 = 10, Bartels, 2003 = 4, Sales et al., 2017 = 1). Additional post-hoc statistical power calculations were performed in R (R Core Team, 2020) using the Monte Carlo simulations which indicated the models of temperature differences before and after contact were sufficiently powered to detect differences in our data set, while the uniformity of the data in the pre-contact stage was underpowered to detect any differences (Table 1). The lower power of the latter test was due to the expected uniformity of measured values.

The participants included were either students or office workers. Before the start of the experiment, participants were briefed about the general purpose of the experiment and signed an informed consent form. Participants did not receive any compensation for participating in the study.

2.2. Study design

A randomised cross-over design was used where all the participants tested all the materials in a randomised order. For this purpose, participants and materials were assigned a unique code. Then, the codes of the materials were randomly assigned to the codes of the participants following a random draw.

The participants made four to five visits in the laboratory. On each visit, the participants underwent one to five sessions (testing different materials). The duration of one session was 45 min (15 min of rest and 30 min of measurement that included 15 min of constant contact with the material and 15 min of answering questions). The contact of 15 min was chosen based on Fiell and Fiel (2013), who suggested that an individual changes posture every 10 or 15 min. Consequently, it is expected that an individual will be in constant contact with the surface no longer than 15 min when performing paper or computer work. Similarly, Sales et al. (2017) also suggested 15 min of contact as the most suitable time for evaluating the temperature of a chair and the rest between consecutive sessions took at least 15 min as suggested by Ring (2014). On testing days, participants were instructed to avoid coffee and other stimulants, alcohol, large meals, smoking, and intense physical exercise. Additionally, participants were advised not to use topical applications on their forearms. During the experiment, all participants wore clothing that exposed their forearms to contact with tabletops.

The study was divided into three parts: i) physical measurements of the tabletop materials, ii) assessing the surface temperature distribution

Table 2
Tabletop materials used in the study.

Material for tabletop	Material treatment
Oak	Untreated
Oak	Lacquer
Oak	Oiled
Spruce	Untreated
Spruce	Lacquer
Spruce	Oiled
Oak Veneer	Untreated
Imitation Wood Laminate	/
MFTC	/
Glass	/

and temperature changes of tabletop materials using infrared thermography before and after 15 min of contact, and iii) answering questions related to perception of the tabletop materials.

The experiment was carried out in an air-conditioned laboratory environment over a period of two months during winter. Environmental parameters (air temperature, relative humidity, and air velocity) were controlled during the study and measured during each session, before and after testing, using Metrel® Multinorm MI 6201 with an A1091 microclimatic probe.

2.3. Tabletop materials

Ten different materials (80 cm × 80 cm × 2 cm), depicted in Table 2, were used as tabletops (Fig. 1) on a wooden table frame (height = 73 cm). Six surfaces were manufactured from solid wood, two were wood composites with particleboard cores (imitation wood laminate - IW laminate - and oak veneer) and two were non-wood materials (MFTC - mineral filled thermoplastic composite (Kerrock®) - and glass). Pictures of all tabletops are available in Supplementary file A.

2.4. Experiment

2.4.1. Measurements of physical material properties

Before the beginning of the measurements, the surface of the samples was cleaned. During the measurements, the samples were placed horizontally, with the inclination of the sample surface of 0°. All measurements were performed under controlled laboratory conditions.

The measurements of thermal effusivity were performed based on DIN 52614 standard (oiled wooden materials were added later in the study and did not undergo the physical measurements). The thermal effusivity of the tabletop materials was measured with a thin heat flux density meter (28.5 × 35.1 mm and 0.18 mm thick) and a standardized heat source. The methodology included the measurement of energy dissipation from a standardized heat source into the sample. Three measurements were performed on each sample to determine the amount of heat dissipated after the first minute and after 10 min. The thermal effusivity was reported in kJ/m².

Material emissivity was determined based on ASTM E1933 standard: Standard Practice for Measuring and Compensating for Emissivity Using Infrared Imaging Radiometers, which prescribes the procedure for radiometric emissivity measurements. Emissivity was measured on samples (3 measurements for each) that were thermalized in a thermally controlled environment to the temperature 10 K warmer than the ambient temperature. The procedure was conducted by using a sample drying oven, a calibrated contact thermometer, Pt100 class A, and a label with known emissivity ($\epsilon = 0.95$).

Additionally, the dimensions and weight of the samples were also measured to determine their density, slipperiness, hardness, and

Fig. 1. Table frames with desktop surfaces made of MFTC (left) and oiled oak (right).

roughness. These results are available online (Podrekar et al., 2020).

2.4.2. Infrared thermography

To assess materials' temperature, change before and after use, infrared thermography has been used, which has been shown to be a suitable method to assess surface temperature in furniture studies (Sales et al., 2017). It is a non-contact, non-invasive and a valid method to evaluate surface skin temperature (Roy et al., 2006). All materials remained in the laboratory at least 24 h prior to the testing. Thermographic pictures were captured using FLIR® E6 thermal camera with 19, 200 pixels, ±2 °C accuracy, and <0.06 °C thermal sensitivity (manufacturer's data). The material emissivity was defined based on laboratory testing whereas, for human skin emissivity, the proposed value from the manufacturer's manual was used (0.98). The camera was positioned 1.5 m above the tabletop surface and aligned at a right angle to the surface.

After arriving to the laboratory, participants rested for 15 min to relax and adjust to the indoor temperature of the room (Ring 2014) and then sat at a randomly assigned table. Immediately before participants sat at the table, tabletop surface temperatures were captured by the thermal camera for the first time. In the next 15 min, the participants' forearms were in constant contact with tabletops. All participants wore clothes that exposed their forearms, allowing direct contact with the tabletop materials. The tabletop surface temperatures were captured for the second time immediately after the subject disengaged contact with the material. The average tabletop surface temperature measured is the pre contact surface temperature indicator used in the study (pre-stage). The average tabletop surface temperature measured from the participants' forearm print on the tabletop (material temperature) is the post-contact surface temperature indicator used in the study (post-stage).

After the second thermal image was captured, participants completed a text transcription task, transcribing a short paragraph on a sheet of paper that was put directly on the tabletop surface. Immediately after transcribing, the participants answered four questions (Table 3) regarding the aesthetics, tactile and practical suitability of the material. Answers to each of the four questions were provided on a 9-point Likert-type scale (1 = especially dislike, 5 = average, 9 = especially like).

Affective states and cognitive performance were measured simultaneously in the same study (Lipovac et al., 2020).

2.5. Image processing

Thermal images were analysed using the OpenCV 3.4 (OpenCV.org) image processing library with Python 3.6 (Python Software Foundation (Rossum, 1995)). Image processing was carried out in three steps: i) manually setting control points on the forearm print on the tabletop, ii) automatically determining the edge of the forearm print on the tabletop based on predefined control points, iii) determining intensity values within the forearm print on the desktop area delimited by the control points.

Four control points for each forearm were determined by selecting them with a mouse on the digital thermal image (Fig. 2a). Based on the control points, we determined the mask of the forearm print area (Fig. 2b) and used only the data within the masked regions for surface temperature analysis. The summary statistics and comparisons presented were based on the data from masked regions of the image.

Table 3

Questions for subjective evaluation of the materials.

	Question
Question 1	How do you like the material for handwriting?
Question 2	How do you like the tactile aspects of the material?
Question 3	How do you like the visual aspects of the material?
Question 4	How do you like the material for everyday use?

Fig. 2. a) Forearm print in a thermal image with control points selected. b) Masked image of the forearm print area.

2.6. Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was conducted in R version 4.0.3 (R Core Team (2020) using RStudio (R Studio (2020)). To test the relationship between the surface temperature of the desk tops and the materials of the desk tops, linear mixed models were fit to the data using the lme4 R package (Bates et al., 2015) with the within-subjects repeated measure as a random effect. The data met the assumptions of this model. Three models were fit. First, a model was fit to test the relationship between the surface temperature of the desktops and material type before contact. The second model tested the relationship between the surface temperature of the desktop and material type, forearm mass, and subject sex after 15 min of contact. The third model tested the difference in the surface temperature and material type between the pre-test and post-test periods. The temperature included in the model was the average value across the selected surface area for both arms, which was measured as described in Section 2.5. Additional versions of the second model were fit to the 10th and 90th quantile of temperature to test for differences at the lower and upper ends of the temperature spectrum. These models provided less explanatory power than the model for the mean (high residual variance and deviance, lower Akaike information criterion, Bayes information Criterion) and the model of the mean was selected and reported here. However, in the model of the 90th quantile of temperature, an effect of subject sex was detected and is reported in the results.

To determine statistical significance, estimate effect-sizes, extract confidence intervals of effect sizes, and conduct pairwise comparisons between materials based on the fitted linear mixed models, the emmeans R package (Lenth, 2019) was used. Using this package, p-values associated with the significance of model parameters (e.g., material type) were calculated using Satterthwaite's method. For pairwise comparisons between methods, the p-values were adjusted using Tukey's method for a family of 10 estimates. Degrees of freedom were calculated using the Kenward-Roger method. The effect sizes and confidence intervals from the fitted models are reported in °C. The observed power of the three linear mixed models was determined by Monte Carlo simulation using the simr R package (Green and MacLeod, 2016) with 1000 simulations. The dataset and processing code are available online (Podrekar et al., 2020).

To compare subjective assessment ratings between materials, we conducted Friedman tests. Separate Friedman tests were conducted for each subjective assessment item as a dependent variable and material as an independent variable; p-values in Friedman tests were adjusted with the Bonferroni correction. Post-hoc pairwise comparisons were conducted with pairwise Wilcoxon two-sample signed rank tests; p-values in pairwise comparisons were adjusted with the Benjamini-Hochberg procedure. Correlations between the tabletop temperatures and subjective assessment ratings are Spearman correlations (0 = none, 0.1–0.2 = poor, 0.3–0.5 = fair, 0.6–0.7 = moderate, 0.8–0.9 = very strong, 1 = perfect (Akoglu, 2018)). The significance threshold was set at $\alpha < 0.05$.

3. Results

3.1. Physical properties of tabletop materials

Measured properties of selected materials, thermal effusivity and emissivity, are presented in Table 4. MFTC and glass had the highest thermal effusivity after one and after 10 min of testing, whereas emissivity was similar across all materials included.

3.2. Infrared thermography

The average ambient temperature in the laboratory during testing was $23.6 \pm 0.7^\circ\text{C}$ and average relative humidity was $37.4 \pm 6.9\%$. The air velocity was below 0.15 m/s. Fig. 3 shows an example of a tabletop thermal image captured at the beginning (Fig. 3a) and after 15 min of constant contact with forearms (Fig. 3b). Surface and arm-print region temperatures were measured 16-times, once for each participant. The mean pre-stage surface temperature of the tabletops differed from the mean post-stage arm contact area (Fig. 4). The degree of difference varied by material type, as well.

The observed surface temperatures of the desktop material at the beginning and after 15 min of contact with subjects are depicted in Table 5. After 15 min of contact, the lowest surface temperature was observed in glass and MFTC (under 30°C), whereas the highest surface temperatures were observed in oak veneer and IW laminate, followed by spruce (lacquered, untreated, oiled) and oak (untreated, oil, lacquered).

The participants' skin temperatures in the area of the forearms were also collected and analysed. Because statistical analyses revealed no significant differences among the temperatures of the participants' forearms (no effect of material type, sex, or forearm mass) detailed results are not presented herein.

3.3. Model fitting and hypothesis testing

Three linear mixed models were fit to test the relationship between surface temperature and material type at different times. In each case, the variance associated with the within-subjects repeated measure

Table 4

The results of physical measurements of thermal effusivity (after one (T1) and 10 (T10) minutes) and emissivity.

Material	T1 (kJ/m ²)	T10 (kJ/m ²)	Emissivity
Oak Untreated	34.62	153.43	0.95
Oak Lacquered	40.81	177.31	0.95
Oak Oiled	/	/	0.95
Spruce Untreated	24.21	93.61	0.90
Spruce Lacquered	28.17	104.60	0.93
Spruce Oiled	/	/	0.95
IW Laminate	37.12	148.22	0.94
Oak Veneer	38.13	153.23	0.92
MFTC	65.72	345.05	0.95
Glass	70.92	326.15	0.97

Fig. 3. a) Thermal image at the pre-stage (before the forearm contact). b) Thermal image at the post-stage (after 15 min of forearm being in contact with material).

Fig. 4. Data distribution of the mean pre-stage surface temperatures of the desktop materials (blue) and the mean post-stage temperatures of the surface arm print region (red). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Table 5

Observed desktop surface temperature before (pre-test stage, full area) and after (post-test stage, arm print area) 15 min of use.

	Pre-test stage			Post-test stage		
	Mean (°C)	SD	Range (°C)	Mean (°C)	SD	Range (°C)
Oak Untreated	24.57	0.87	21.99 to 26.70	30.59	0.96	27.33 to 32.66
Oak Oiled	24.48	1.19	21.40 to 26.50	30.56	0.77	27.23 to 32.53
Oak Lacquered	24.52	0.62	23.26 to 26.42	30.50	1.01	27.32 to 32.85
Spruce Untreated	24.63	1.10	22.35 to 27.35	31.23	0.91	27.28 to 32.82
Spruce Oiled	24.88	0.87	23.22 to 26.79	31.14	1.02	28.18 to 33.13
Spruce Lacquered	24.56	0.69	23.23 to 26.66	31.41	0.98	28.32 to 34.14
IW Laminate	24.67	1.06	21.45 to 27.37	31.37	0.76	28.91 to 33.23
Oak Veneer	24.78	3.86	22.97 to 26.83	31.72	4.45	28.60 to 33.04
MFTC	24.99	0.98	22.44 to 27.74	29.95	0.93	27.05 to 32.41
Glass	24.61	0.67	23.04 to 26.83	29.83	0.88	26.76 to 31.48

random effect was small.

3.3.1. Desktop surface temperatures before testing

There were no statistically significant differences in pre-test stage desktop surface temperature. This was expected as the materials were held at room temperature for 24 h before readings were taken. Given this time, the desktops were expected to reach equilibrium temperature with their environment. The within-subjects variance was 0.31 and the residual variance was 0.58.

3.3.2. Desktop surface temperatures after testing

The mean temperature of the arm print area on the desktop surfaces after testing varied by material, but not by subject sex or forearm mass (Fig. 5). All materials had higher surface temperatures than glass (the reference material in the model) except for MFTC. Glass and MFTC had the lowest surface temperature after testing (glass: mean = 29.8°C, 95% CI = 29.4°C to 30.2°C; MFTC: mean = 30.0°C, 95% CI = 29.6°C to 30.4°C). Oak veneer had the highest surface temperature after testing (mean = 31.7°C, 95% CI = 31.2°C to 32.1°C). The within-subjects variance was 0.29 and the residual variance was 0.44. The 90th quantile of temperature was estimated to be 0.6° less after 15 min of contact by female participants than by male participants across all materials.

Pairwise comparisons reveal that all materials except MFTC differ from glass. Oak veneer had a higher surface temperature after 15 min of contact than any of the other oak-based desktops by roughly 1 °C (Table 6).

Besides glass and MFTC, there was suggestive evidence that IW laminate surface temperatures differed from oak oiled and oak

Fig. 5. Mean arm print area surface temperature (with 95% CI) after 15 min of contact for each material type.

Table 6

Surface temperature differences between oak-based desktops.

Oak Veneer compared to:	Temperature difference (°C)	95% CI (°C)	p-value
Oak Oiled	1.08	0.32 to 1.84	0.0004
Oak Lacquered	1.07	0.31 to 1.83	0.0005
Oak Untreated	1.02	0.26 to 1.78	0.0012

Table 7

Surface temperature differences between IW Laminate and other materials.

IW Laminate compared to:	Temperature difference (°C)	95% CI (°C)	p-value
Glass	1.55	0.79 to 2.31	<0.0001
MFTC	1.36	2.11 to 0.60	<0.0001
Oak Untreated	0.71	1.46 to -0.05	0.0907
Oak Oiled	0.76	1.52 to 0.01	0.0464
Oak Lacquered	0.76	1.52 to 0.00	0.0494
Spruce Untreated	0.21	0.96 to -0.55	0.9969
Spruce Oiled	0.29	1.05 to -0.47	0.9669
Spruce Lacquered	0.11	0.87 to -0.65	0.9999

lacquered. No significant difference was observed between IW laminate and spruce-based materials and oak untreated. (Table 7).

The surface treatment applied to the solid wood desktops (spruce, oak) had no apparent impact on the surface temperature after contact (p-value > 0.05 in all comparisons within solid wood species groups). Additional pairwise comparisons are available online (Podrekar et al., 2020).

3.3.3. Temperature change between pre- and post-stage measurements

To determine if there were differences in the degree of change in temperature before and after, a linear mixed model was fit using the post-stage surface temperature minus the pre-stage temperature as the dependent variable. The within-subjects variance was 0.65 and the residual variance was 0.63. Wood composite materials (oak veneer, IW laminate) experienced the greatest change in surface temperature, while the solid spruce materials followed closely. The solid oak desktops were grouped together after the spruce tabletops. In each of these cases (solid spruce, solid oak, and wood composites), there was significant overlap in the confidence intervals, indicating the surface temperature changes

were not appreciably different. However, the temperature changes of both glass and MFTC desktops were notably lower between the pre- and post-stage (Fig. 6).

3.4. Subjective assessment of materials

Results of the subjective assessment of materials of the four items are presented in Fig. 7. Friedman tests comparing the subjective assessment scores between materials detected a statistically significant difference in perceived tactile pleasantness ($\chi^2(9) = 38.26, p < 0.001$), visual pleasantness ($\chi^2(9) = 41.58, p < 0.001$), and suitability for everyday use ($\chi^2(9) = 46.42, p < 0.001$), while no significant differences were detected in perceived suitability for writing ($\chi^2(9) = 16.73, p = 0.053$). The statistically significant results from post-hoc pairwise comparisons with Wilcoxon signed-rank tests are displayed in Fig. 7; the complete results are available online (Podrekar et al., 2020). Wooden materials were generally perceived as more pleasing to touch and more visually appealing as well as more suitable for everyday use than glass and/or MFTC.

Participants rated spruce lacquered as the most pleasant to touch (median = 8; inter-quartile range (IQR) = 7 to 8), while glass received the lowest scores (median = 5; IQR = 3 to 6), followed by MFTC (median = 5; IQR = 4 to 6). The participants rated oak oiled and IW laminate as the most pleasant to see (for both median = 8; IQR = 7 to 9). MFTC was rated as the least visually pleasant (median = 3.5; IQR = 2.5 to 6). Spruce lacquered was rated as the most suitable for writing (median = 7.5; IQR = 6 to 9), whereas oak untreated had the lowest ratings (median = 5; IQR = 3 to 6.25). The highest ratings for everyday use were given to IW laminate (median = 8; IQR = 6.25 to 8.25), followed by spruce lacquered (median = 7; IQR = 6 to 8), oak lacquered (median = 7; IQR = 5.75 to 8), and oak oiled (median = 7; IQR = 5 to 7.25). MFTC and glass were rated as the least suitable for everyday use (median = 4; IQR = 1 to 4.25; median = 4; IQR = 2.75 to 4.25, respectively).

Additionally, we examined the relationship among material features (thermal effusivity, temperature) and subjective perception of the material. A very strong association was found between materials considered to be pleasant to the touch and suitable for everyday use ($r = 0.93, p = 0.001$). Higher material thermal effusivity was moderately associated with lower surface temperature after 15 min of contact ($r = -0.76, p = 0.028$). There was a trend indicating that materials with lower thermal effusivity (warmer materials) received a higher rating for tactile pleasantness, but it was not statistically significant ($r = -0.69, p = 0.058$). No other significant associations were found among objective and subjective data.

Fig. 6. Temperature differences between the pre-test surface temperature of the desktop and the post-test arm print area surface temperature of the desktop for each material (mean and 95% CI).

Fig. 7. Results of subjective assessment of materials.

4. Discussion

This study investigated thermal characteristics and user perceptions of ten different materials used for tablespots. Materials with lower thermal effusivity (wood-based materials) were in general warmer after 15 min of contact with forearms and were rated as more pleasantly haptic and more suitable for writing. Both wood-based materials and imitation wood materials were rated as the most pleasant to see and most suitable for everyday use.

Skin surface temperature of the human body varies approximately between 33 °C and 34 °C, however, it depends on different factors, such

as air temperature (Liu et al., 2013) and radiation (Wang et al., 2013). Marrakchi and Maibach (2007) reported an average forearm temperature of 32.8 ± 1.7 °C in young adults, which is comparable to our results, where participants' mean forearm temperature was 32.6 ± 0.9 °C. Similarly to Liu et al. (2011), we found no significant differences in measured skin temperature between males and females, although cooling responses could differ between sexes with females having faster skin cooling compared to males under slow cooling conditions, most probably because of the differences in hand size and shape (Jay and Havenith, 2004).

In our study, the temperature of the tablespots was lower than skin

surface temperature as it ranged between 24 and 25 °C. When the participants had their forearms in contact with the tabletops, the forearms were acting as a source of heat, transferring heat from the forearms to the material. Since the source of heat (forearms) was similar for all repeated measurements, the tabletop temperature after contact depended on the thermal effusivity of the materials measured. This influenced thermal sensation and consequently user's perceived thermal comfort of the material (Sakuragawa et al., 1991). Because office workers or students in schools spend a considerable time in direct contact with the tabletop, it is important that the material is thermally comfortable. Minimising sensations of cold in distal parts of the body is relevant because the overall sensation of cold is more likely to appear in the limbs, followed by the proximal body parts (Yao et al., 2016). The local thermal sensation model by Zhang et al. (2010) suggests that local thermal sensation is a function of the local skin temperature, whole body temperature, and the rate of temperature change over time. In this study, only the local temperature on the forearm region has been altered by different materials with different thermal effusivity. It should be noted that the model by Zhang et al. (2010) and many other studies assessing thermal comfort (Deng et al., 2017; Fang et al., 2018), considered changes in skin temperature due to convection (e.g., using air to cool or heat body parts) whereas in our study, the participants were in constant contact with the tabletop material. Nevertheless, the perception of thermal comfort in local body parts is important as it has been shown that the overall body thermal comfort will follow the parts of the body that feel the most uncomfortable (Yao et al., 2016). Investigations of the simultaneous effects of other factors, such as room temperature and participants' clothing insulation should be assessed in future studies.

The first hypothesis, stating that wood-based materials have higher post surface temperature differences than non-wood materials, is inconclusive. The highest post surface temperature difference was observed for oak veneer, followed by IW laminate and then solid wood materials. A possible explanation for this could be that veneer and laminate have a higher material density compared to solid wood materials, which leads to a faster and higher temperature change, since the amount of heat a material can absorb also depends on the material density (Czajkowski et al., 2016). The substrate the IW laminate and veneers were applied to also likely played a role in the post surface temperature difference. For both surface types, this was wood-based particleboard. No significant correlation was observed between temperature after contact and subjective perception of suitability for everyday use and pleasantness to touch. This is in concordance with Vlaović et al. (2012) who also found no association between chair temperature and subjective evaluation of thermal comfort (except for the thigh region). On the other hand, Kotradyová and Teischinger (2014a,b) found that thermal conductivity of the material is related to the perception of thermal comfort with warmer materials being more thermally comfortable. In a study by Sales et al. (2017), the highest change in temperature (7.8 °C) was observed in a plywood seat, whereas in our study oak veneer had the largest increase in average surface temperature (6.9 °C). In both studies, the lowest change in temperature was observed mostly among non-wooden materials. Higher changes in temperature of the seat pans could appear due to clothing insulation which decreased the heat transfer between objects or because different materials were used. Since the change in temperature of the material was similar, this indicates that comparable changes in materials' temperature can be observed in seat pans after seating or in tabletops after constant contact while performing paper or computer work.

Pairwise comparisons of tabletop surface temperatures after contact revealed that not only were all materials other than MFTC different from glass, but there were also many other notable differences. Significant differences were observed between oak veneer and other oak-based tabletops, with oak veneer having higher surface temperature differences after 15 min by roughly 1 °C. These differences could partly be explained by different thermal effusivity characteristics of the composite material

(oak veneer overlaid on particleboard) compared to the solid oak materials. Different treatments of oak based materials were also shown to affect physiological status of an individual, where oiled and vitreous finished oak samples decreased cortex activity and heart rate while no such effect was found for mirror treatment of oak (Ikei et al., 2017b). The surface treatment applied to the solid wood desktops (spruce, oak) had no evident impact on the surface post temperature, which is also comparable with thermal effusivity results among spruce- and oak-based materials. On the other hand, surface treatment notably influenced the user's perception of tabletop materials. In our study the highest haptic suitability was found among wood materials with lacquered surface treatment, which confirms the second hypothesis. Harris et al. (2021) considers friction and roughness as important features that influence the tactile perception of materials, where low friction and smooth topography increases the perceived pleasantness of the material. In our study, when assessing tactile suitability of the material the participants also looked at the material, hence the effect of visual impact was not controlled. Nonetheless, the results suggest that wood may be the most suitable haptic material for school or office desks if it has an acceptable surface treatment. Our study indicates this is lacquer.

Wood is highly appreciated material in furniture and interior design (Manuel et al., 2015) and positive effects, such as reduction of stress, due to visual exposure to wood have been reported (Burnard and Kutnar, 2015; Lipovac et al., 2020; Sun et al., 2020). Wood is also well perceived by individuals and described as warm, natural, and harmonious (Biggsby et al., 2005; Nordvik et al., 2009). The colour and grain were recognised as important wood features for consumers to form their preferences on visual pleasantness of different wood samples (Biggsby et al., 2005). In our study, the participants rated oak-based materials higher on visual pleasantness compared to other materials. This could be explained by grey hue patterns which are common in oak-based materials. Homogeneous visual appearance and moderate colour intensity, which were characteristic of oak used in our study, have also been preferred by consumers of wooden deck materials (Nyrud et al., 2008). In addition, naturalness of wood could have played a role in its positive evaluation: wood is perceived as natural (Burnard et al., 2017) and people tend to prefer natural elements and patterns (Kellert, 2008). MFTC received the lowest scores in visual pleasantness, which could be because of the red hue and non-natural appearance of the material. The red hue could have been considered as too stimulating for indoor spaces, and the lack of naturalness could have conflicted with the general human preference for natural surroundings. Although participants in our study preferred the greyish appearance of oak, the determination of the most suitable visual appearance of desk materials needs further investigations with larger sample heterogeneity and larger sample size as it has been shown that differences in colour perception and preference exist among young participants (Mohebbi, 2014) as well as among adults (Ling et al., 2006). In addition to hue, future studies should consider other visual properties of wooden materials, such as particular characteristics of the wood grain. Finally, studies should examine how the context of wood use can influence human preference. For example, people may prefer lighter wooden materials in general (Fujisaki et al., 2015) but darker wooden materials for outdoor use (Lipovac et al., 2019).

The participants rated the lacquered spruce as the most suitable for writing, which confirms the first part of hypothesis three. The lowest rating gained oak untreated, indicating that surface treatment could play an important role when assessing material's suitability for handwriting. The lacquered treatment provides a hard-top coat that is more suitable for writing than soft untreated wood. The second part of hypothesis three can also be confirmed, as wood-based materials with lacquer finishing received higher ratings for everyday use, compared to untreated and oiled wood materials. MFTC and glass were rated as the least appropriate materials for everyday use. A similar trend was shown in the study by Kotradyová (2015) in which chairs made of untreated spruce were rated as the most comfortable, while an aluminium chair was considered the least appropriate by the participants. The preference

of different wood finishing for chairs and tabletops could be explained by the material's hardness. Wood materials with lower hardness tend to be favoured for sitting whereas a stiffer upper surface, such as lacquered, could be more suitable for tabletops because of being more suitable for hand-writing and also resistant to wear. Offices with furniture made of wood are also suggested because of its possible influence on stress reduction (Lipovac and Burnard, 2020; Burnard and Kutnar, 2019; Sun et al., 2020).

Different characteristics of materials influence product purchase. We could divide them into subjective factors, such as perception of the material (aesthetics, usability), objective factors (hardness, roughness, conductivity), and ergonomic factors (shape, colour, security, interaction, function), which are involved in the first evaluation, even if the user is not in contact with the product (Chávez et al., 2015). Choosing the most appropriate material for tabletops is complex and should not be determined only by visual appearance of the material. Results of our study indicate, that when defining which material is the most suitable for everyday use, it is also important that the material is haptically pleasant. Nevertheless, when designing office or school desk, all characteristics should be considered.

5. Study limitations

For more credible results, the participants should be exposed to tabletop materials for a longer period of at least one working day (8 h) to obtain a more reliable subjective perception of the materials. Furthermore, the experiment was conducted in optimal indoor environmental conditions that are not always present in real-life settings. The thermal comfort of materials in warmer or colder indoor environments might differ. Another limitation of the study was the lack of secondary check of the measured temperature (e. g. black box of known temperature).

6. Conclusion

The study evaluated thermal effusivity and perception of different materials being used for school/office tabletop. Sixteen participants tested ten materials in randomised order. The results of our study indicate some practical recommendations, which could be applied when designing desks:

- Tabletop materials with lower thermal effusivity (wood-based materials) were rated as more pleasant to touch compared with glass tabletops and MFTC tabletop.
- Glass and MFTC tabletops had the lowest increase in temperature after 15 min of contact and were rated as least suitable for everyday use.
- The participants most appreciated visual appearance of oak-based materials.
- Lacquered solid wood had the most favourable properties as a tabletop material.

The results of this study suggest that wooden materials may be the most suitable choice for school/office tabletop use, especially when combined with a lacquer surface treatment. On the other hand, glass tabletops and tabletops made of artificial materials, such as MFTC, should be avoided when designing office or school desks. Additionally, the study also suggests that infrared thermography could be a useful tool to objectively assess the surface temperatures behaviour when comparing products and may be helpful in inferring thermal comfort. Future studies, with larger sample size, should investigate the simultaneous effects of several factors, such as room temperature, participants' clothing insulation, and tabletop materials, on different age groups (children, students, adults).

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgement

The authors would like to thank Gregor Podrekar, whose expertise in image processing greatly assisted the research.

The authors acknowledge the European Commission for funding the InnoRenew CoE project (Grant Agreement #739574) under the Horizon2020 Widespread-Teaming program and the Republic of Slovenia (Investment funding of the Republic of Slovenia and the European Union of the European regional Development Fund). The authors would like to acknowledge the financial support by the Slovenian Research Agency through the infrastructure grant no. IO-0035.

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